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SURGICAL WOUND MANAGEMENT WITH VACUUM ASSISTED DRESSING

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ABSTRACT

Background and Objectives: To evaluate the role and efficiency of vacuum dressing in the healing of wounds and to assess the benefits and limitations of using vacuum dressing in different types/categories of wound.

Methods: The study of 25 cases was conducted in the Department of Surgery of a tertiary care teaching hospital over a period of 2 years.

Results: Vacuum dressing had a significant effect on the final outcome of wounds. Wounds which seemingly needed a flap surgery in the first impression, with successive application of vacuum dressing cycles, could be covered with a simple split thickness skin graft. Many patients were salvaged from a revision amputation as shown by the decrease in overall amputation rates.

Interpretation and Conclusion: Based on the data from the present study and other studies available, vacuum dressing results in better healing, with minimal complications, and thus looks to be a promising alternative for the management of various wounds. Vacuum dressing leads to faster healing of the wounds, therefore decreasing the overall hospital stay. Hence, it is cost effective also. It reduces the inconvenience and discomfort caused to the patient by frequent change in dressings. It helps in reducing size of the wounds, has profound effect on wound depth and granulation as seen in our study. It promotes granulation tissue completely covering the tendon, thus enabling simple techniques (e.g., skin graft) rather than formal flap closure in few cases. Wounds with exposed underlying bone and chronic non-healing ulcers can be managed well with vacuum dressing. It reduces the number of amputations and debridement required. More number of wounds can be managed successfully with secondary closure or skin grafting after multiple cycles of vacuum dressing. This reduces patient morbidity and minimizes the overall effect on his quality of life. Good outcome of vacuum dressing also depends on its proper application.

Keywords: surgical wound management, vacuum assisted dressing, chronic wound

Introduction

A wound is defined as an injury creating a disruption in the normal anatomical structure and function of the skin⁽¹⁾. There are two different types of wounds: vulnus that is an acute wound, which heals according to the normal wound healing process, and ulcus that is defined as hard-to-heal wounds (labelled chronic wounds) such as leg ulcers, pressure sore and diabetic foot ulcer. These wounds have a duration of more than six weeks and often show a disturbed wound healing process due to underlying causes other than direct trauma.

The increasing number of chronic and complex wounds poses a growing medical challenge with a high socioeconomic impact and a significant burden to the individual patient. The management of chronic wounds places a considerable burden on health services as it requires considerable manpower, frequent specialist consultation, and adjunct therapies. Generally, figures presented on the cost of wound care only reflect the direct medical costs, and do not include the pain, frustration, economic loss, number of working days lost or impaired quality of life of the patients and their families, or the burden on the health care system or society in general.

Fortunately, several important changes in the principles of wound care have taken place in recent decades. Based on these new insights, a wide range of wound care techniques has been introduced. One of the most significant discoveries in wound management in recent decades was the improvement in wounds with Negative Pressure (vacuum) assisted Wound Therapy (NPWT). Vacuum assisted closure is a universally accepted method for dressing. It has proved its efficacy for wound dressing: faster wound healing, shorter hospital stays⁽²⁾.

Vacuum Assisted Closure (also called vacuum therapy, vacuum sealing or topical negative pressure therapy) is a sophisticated development of a standard surgical procedure: the use of vacuum assisted drainage to remove blood or serous fluid from a wound or operation site. It promotes wound healing by applying a vacuum through a special sealed dressing. The continued vacuum draws out fluid from the wound and increases blood flow to the area. The vacuum may be applied continuously or intermittently, depending on the type of the wound and clinical objectives. The dressings used for the technique include open-cell foam dressings and gauze, sealed with an occlusive dressing intended to contain the vacuum at the wound site. Negative Pressure assisted Wound Therapy (NPWT) devices allow delivery of fluids, such as saline or antibiotics to irrigate the wound (intermittent removal of used fluid supports the cleaning and drainage of the wound bed.)⁽³⁾

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study of 25 cases was conducted in the Department of Surgery of a tertiary care teaching hospital over a period of 2 years. All relevant patients who underwent vacuum dressing were enrolled in the study after taking informed consent. Relevant clinical investigations of patients like local part x-rays, Doppler of limbs (if the wound was present on the limbs), wound culture report and routine blood investigations were recorded in case record form. The number of days per cycle and the total number of cycles for which the patient underwent vacuum dressing were noted. Wound parameters like length, breadth, depth, edge, granulation tissue and amount of slough were noted both pre vacuum dressing and post vacuum dressing and the outcome was calculated. All selected cases were studied from admission up to the complete healing of wounds. Final outcome of the wound and complications of vacuum dressing, if any, were also noted.

Approval from Institute Research Council or Ethics Committees (IRB) has not been taken.

INCLUSION CRITERIA: (1) All patients who underwent application of vacuum dressing over a wound site. (2) Wound sites over any part of the body over which

vacuum dressing was done.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA: (1) Wound having a fistula to organ or body cavity. (2) Necrotic tissue in wound. (3) Patients who did not consent to the procedure. (4) Patients who took discharge against medical advice before completion of treatment of the wound.

RESULTS

AGE DISTRIBUTION

Out of 25 patients of in my study, most patients were of more than 40 years of age. Only 16% patients were less than 20 years of age. Most common age group was 40-60 years (48%). 20% patients were more than 70 years of age.

Table 1: Age distribution of patients

GENDER DISTRIBUTION

In my study, 21 (84%) patients were male and 4 (16%) were female.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS

Majority patients (68%) belonged to lower socio-economic status. (Modified Kuppaswamy classification system was used to categorize patients into various socio-economic strata.)

The increased prevalence of chronic non healing wounds in this category can be attributed to poor hygiene, poor footwear leading to more frequent trauma, less awareness and hospital consultation for wounds and relatively poor nutritional status.

HOSPITAL STAY

In my study, average length of hospital stay was 30 days. Maximum stay was of 92 days in a patient of abdominal wound. Minimum stay was in a patient of 12 days in a patient of upperlimb wound

SITE OF WOUND

Most of the wounds were present on lower limbs (68%). Out of them some patients had isolated foot or leg involvement, while some had extensive involvement of lower limbs. Few had wounds over amputation sites. There were 3 cases of bed sore over lower back region.

There was 1 case of wound over abdomen in which vacuum dressing was applied.

Table 2: Sites of wounds **AETIOLOGY OF WOUND**

In this study, most common an etiology of wound was diabetic foot (32%), followed by arterial insufficiency (24%). Some patients had multifactorial an etiology- such as peripheral vascular disease plus pre-existing diabetes. Other miscellaneous a etiological factors included post abdominal surgery wound dehiscence, large abscess incision and drainage leading to raw area formation, fasciotomy following compartment syndrome, acute infective eczema progressing to cellulitis in a non-diabetic patient (5).

Table 3: Aetiology of wound

CO-MORBIDITIES

Diabetes Mellitus was present in 15 cases (60%), while rest 10 patients (40%) were non-diabetics. Hence diabetes is a significant contributing factor in chronic non-healing wounds. ⁽⁶⁾

Table 4: Comorbidities as a contributing factor in non healing wounds

Co-morbidity	Number of patients
Diabetes mellitus	15 (60%)
Hypertension	10 (40%)
Cardiac diseases	8 (32%)
Thyroid diseases	2 (8%)

SMOKING

Out of 25 patients, 18 patients were smokers (72%). While remaining 7 (28%) were non-smokers. Out of these 18 smokers, 6 patients had developed peripheral vascular disease with non-healing wounds.

The association between cigarette smoking and delayed wound healing is well recognized in clinical practice, although extensive controlled studies have yet to be performed. The documented effects of the toxic constituents of cigarette smoke--particularly nicotine, carbon monoxide, and hydrogen cyanide--suggest potential mechanisms by which smoking may undermine expeditious wound repair.

GRANULATION TISSUE

Maximum patients had pale granulation before vacuum dressing was applied (48%). After the dressing, maximum patients showed improvement in granulation tissue from pink to bright red color (40%). Also, an increase in the amount of granulation

was noted in the form of decreased depth of wounds. ⁽⁷⁾

Organisms Cultured From Wound	Number of Cases
No Growth	3 (12%)
Staphylococcus aureus	10 (40%)
Coagulase negative staphylococcus	2 (8%)
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	6 (24%)
E. Coli	3 (12%)
Proteus mirabilis	1 (4%)
Klebsiella pneumoniae	8 (32%)
Acinetobacter baumannii	7 (28%)
Citrobacter freundii	1 (4%)
Candida species	1 (4%)
Morganella Morgagni	1 (4%)
Gas gangrene positive	2 (8%)

WOUND CULTURE REPORT

In my study, many cases showed growth of multiple organisms simultaneously. Antibiotic Sensitivity reports were collected and patients treated accordingly. Swabs were repeated multiple times until no growth of organism was seen. Most common organism cultured was *Staphylococcus aureus* (40%) followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in 32%.

Table 5: Organism cultured from the wound

LENGTH OF WOUND

In my study, majority patients had wound length in the range of 8.1-10 cm before vacuumdressing. Post dressing maximum patients showed a wound length of 6.1-8 cm. vacuum dressing decreased the wound length by 22.5% on an average.

BREADTH OF WOUND:

In my study, majority patients had wound breadth in the range of 6.1-8 cm before vacuumdressing. Post dressing maximum patients showed a wound breadth of 4.1-6 cm. vacuum dressing decreased the wound breadth by 28.5% on an average.

DEPTH OF WOUND

In my study, majority patients had wound depth in the range of 3.1-4 cm before vacuumdressing. Post dressing maximum patients showed a wound depth of 2.1-3 cm. vacuum dressing decreased the wound depth by 33.3% on an average.

6 patients had a depth of more than 5 cm before vacuum dressing. After the dressing, only 3 patients had more than 5 cm deep wounds. (50% reduction in the number of patients). Minimum depth of less than 2 cm was seen in 3 patients pre vacuum dressing. Post the dressing the number of patients with wound depth less than 2 cm increased to 6. This shows a significant effect of vacuum dressing in depth of wounds.

COMPLICATIONS OF VACUUM DRESSING

Out of 25, 6 (24%) patients complained of a tingling sensation and local site itching while the suction was applied. Only 1 (4%) patient had skin reaction in the form of rashes under the bandaged site which subsided subsequently. No patient reported of serious complications of vacuum dressing.

FINAL SURGICAL OUTCOME

Vacuum dressing had a significant effect on the final outcome of wounds. Wounds which seemingly needed a flap surgery in the first impression, with successive application of vacuum dressing cycles, could be covered with a simple split thickness skin graft. Many patients were salvaged of a revision amputation as showed by the decrease in overall amputation rates.

Majority patients underwent split thickness skin grafting or secondary suturing post sessions of vacuum dressing.

In few large wounds with exposed bony areas, bone drilling was done to granulate the wound followed by a flap surgery to cover the defect.

Application of vacuum dressing over large ulcer over lower limb following debridement: (a) wound immediately after debridement, (b) application of vacuum dressing over wound, (c) wound after removal of vacuum dressing after 3 days.

DISCUSSION

WOUNDS AND WOUND HEALING:

A wound is defined as an injury creating a disruption in the normal anatomical structure and function of the skin. There are two different types of wounds: vulnus that is an acute wound, which heals according to the normal wound healing process, and ulcer that is defined as hard-to-heal wounds (previously labelled chronic wounds) such as leg ulcers, pressure ulcers and diabetic foot ulcer. These wounds have a duration of more than six weeks and often show a disturbed wound healing process due to underlying causes other than direct trauma.

Wound healing is a dynamic, interactive process involving soluble mediators, blood cells, extracellular matrix components, resident cells (keratinocytes, fibroblasts, endothelial cells, nerve cells), and infiltrating leukocyte subtypes in a complex and highly orchestrated sequence of cellular and biochemical changes^[8]

Wounds may heal by three principles: primary, secondary or tertiary healing⁽⁹⁾. Primary healing occurs when the wound edges are put together, often with sutures, and healing occurs with minimal tissue defects. Secondary healing occurs in open wounds, when the wound edges are not put together and healing occurs with formation of granulation tissue. Tertiary healing is delayed primary healing and

occurs when a wound is allowed to heal openly for a few days and then is closed with secondary sutures.

PHASES OF WOUND HEALING ⁽¹⁰⁾:

The classic model of normal wound healing is divided into three sequential, yet overlapping, phases:

Inflammatory
Proliferative
Remodeling

NEGATIVE PRESSURE WOUND THERAPY (NPWT) OR VACUUM ASSISTED CLOSURE (VAC)

Pseudonyms:

TNP (Topical Negative Pressure), VST (Vacuum Sealing Technique) and SSS (Sealed Surface wound Suction).

Ideal Method of application:

It consists of a device that creates a vacuum in the wound using a wound filler of polyurethane foam, polyvinyl alcohol foam dressing or gauze.

The foam, or gauze, is adapted exactly after the size of the wound (a) then the wound filler and the entire wound are covered with a transparent adhesive drape (b). A hole is cut in the drape and a suction tube is adapted (c). The tube is connected to the vacuum machine and a sub-atmospheric pressure of normally 80-125 mmHg is applied (d), dependent on which system use

Continuous, intermittent and variable negative pressure ^[11]

In negative suction dressing, the negative pressure is most commonly applied in the “continuous mode”, i.e., the pressure is constant. However, the negative pressure can be repeatedly switched on and off, alternating between atmospheric and sub-atmospheric pressure; this is called “intermittent pressure” therapy. Treatment is usually applied in 5- minute-on/2-minute-off cycles ^[12], based on a study by Morykwas *et al.* It has been shown that the amount of granulation tissue formed in the wound bed is greater during intermittent negative suction compared to continuous therapy. This may be the result of both mechanical stimulations of the wound bed and altered blood flow, which may enhance tissue oxygenation and angiogenesis. Intermittent pressure therapy entails sudden changes in pressure that cause the foam to expand and contract over the granulation tissue, which may lead to pain. “Variable pressure” therapy has, therefore, been introduced, providing smoother variations between the two different levels of negative pressure, thereby maintaining a negative pressure throughout the treatment.

MECHANISM OF ACTION OF VACUUM ASSISTED CLOSURE:

1. Wound contraction,
2. Stimulation of granulation tissue formation,
3. Continuous wound cleansing after adequate primary surgical debridement,
4. Continuous removal of exudate, and
5. Reduction of interstitial oedema

Following are the common indications of vacuum dressing:

Acute/traumatic wounds
Open abdominal wounds
Dehiscenced sternal wounds following cardiac surgery

Failed Split-thickness skin graft

Fasciotomy

Diabetic foot ulcers

Venous leg ulcers after the underlying etiology have been corrected.

Pressure ulcers

Post amputation stump infections

COMPLICATIONS OF VACUUM DRESSING:

Complications and adverse events associated with vacuum dressings have not been thoroughly investigated but reports of complications are present in the literature. Complications in terms of bleeding causing severe injuries and death have been described, mainly associated with vascular grafts, sternal and groin wounds and anticoagulant therapy.

Pain was the most frequently cited reason for terminating the vacuum dressing. Pain was reported during dressing changes and the pain rating was higher in the group using foam as wound filler compared to gauze, which may be due to adhesion and tissue in-growth caused by the effect of the foam.

A case report of toxic shock syndrome after vacuum dressing was also reported in one study.

Limitations of mobility and a deterioration of the physical functioning was a complication.

Fluid depletion- This problem should be considered and managed appropriately where large amounts of effluent are collected.

CONCLUSION

Vacuum dressing is a recent modality of treatment of wounds. Its introduction has changed the course of management of wounds. Based on the data from the present study and other studies available, vacuum dressing results in better healing, with minimal complications, and thus looks to be a promising alternative for the management of various wounds.

Vacuum dressing leads to faster healing of the wounds, therefore decreasing the overall hospital stay. Hence, it is cost effective also. It reduces the inconvenience and discomfort caused to the patient by frequent change in dressings. It helps in reducing size of the wounds, has profound effect on wound depth and granulation as seen in my study. It promotes granulation tissue completely covering the tendon, thus enabling simple techniques (e.g., skin graft) rather than formal flap closure in a few cases.

Wounds with exposed underlying bone and chronic non-healing ulcers can be managed well with vacuum dressing. It reduces the number of amputations and re-debridement required. More number of wounds can be managed successfully with secondary closure or skin grafting after multiple cycles of vacuum dressing. This reduces patient⁽²⁾ morbidity and minimizes the overall effect on his quality of life. Good outcome of vacuum dressing also depends on its proper application.

Conflict of Interest:

Nil

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